

Popular Article

Application of GIS to Ensuring Food Security

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Abstract

In order to feed the world's rapidly growing population, currently, about 8.2 billion, with the crop productivity of about 2.1 billion tonnes, and according to the World Bank report, the population will increase to about 9.7 billion, and hence the estimated productivity will be about 3.3 billion tonnes, we have been able to increase agricultural production due to technology being advance in few past decades. However, we also face numerous issues today, like shrinking cropland, depleting water supplies, and climate change, which emphasize the necessity of taking previously unheard-of steps to attain agricultural resilience to provide food for everyone. To monitor crops and implement targeted & optimal management practices that will increase crop productivity, geographic information systems and other technologies like remote sensing, global positioning systems etc. have been essential. In this article we discuss the application of GIS that helps boost efficiency and production thus help in problems of food security.

Keywords: GIS, GPS, Precision Agriculture, Remote sensing

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Introduction

There is a rising need to increase and improve the utilisation of agricultural land in order to meet the increasing demand for food and agricultural commodities, which further put extra strains on natural resources. According to World Health Organization (WHO), food security can be achieved if everyone has access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food throughout the year. To achieve food security as long we have been able to increase agricultural production due to technology being advance in few past decades. In various technology one is geographic information system (GIS). A geographic information system (GIS) is a computer program used to document, store, validate, and display data about places on Earth's surface (Maguire, 1991). A GIS may display a wide variety of data types, including streets, buildings, and plants, on a single map. People can perceive, evaluate, and comprehend structures and connections simply as a result. Geographer Roger Tomlinson first coined the term geographic information system (GIS) in 1963 and is known as the "father of GIS." GIS is a tool in precision agriculture because of its support for feature and location data collection, storage, retrieval, and analysis, as well as its usefulness for data-driven solutions, particularly in site-specific management. In contrast to traditional maps, digital GIS maps contain multiple layers of data, each of which presents a map or information about a specific attribute, such as yield, pest infestation, nutrient status, soil survey, precipitation, etc. Furthermore, GIS offers the analytical capacity to extract inter-

relationships between features through the use of statistical tools and geospatial analytics. The insights thus obtained are useful for management practice decision-making. GIS is essential for maintaining food security in a world where population expansion, resource constraints, agricultural land limitations, and climate change are all becoming more significant issues. GIS offers powerful tools to address the complexities of food security by enhancing precision in agriculture, improving resource allocation, and mitigating risks. By bridging the gap between geographical data and agricultural decision-making, GIS enables farmers to minimise their environmental impacts while optimising resource utilization. By customising precision agriculture techniques to particular field circumstances, this technology-driven method helps boost efficiency and production.

APPLICATIONS OF GIS TO ENSURING FOOD SECURITY:

Various Applications of GIS to ensuring food security is depicted in fig. given below and described one by one.

Fig. Various application of GIS to ensuring food security

1. **Precision Agriculture:** Precision farming aims to improve the management of inputs, including seeds, fertiliser, pesticides, herbicides, and water, by applying the appropriate amounts of inputs at the appropriate times and locations. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are used in precision agriculture to help farmers make decisions by managing spatial information. Thus, we apply the right amount of water, fertiliser, and pesticide where they are needed, ensuring that they are allocated where they are needed the most (Earl et al., 1996). It can also create

detailed maps of vegetation and productivity, including crop information, soil type, and elevation; identify problematic areas of their fields that need special attention; and help farmers make decisions to improve future yields, such as adjusting irrigation or amending soil nutrients. Traditional soil mapping focuses on a typical soil property from a point of emphasis, which has the drawback of failing to capture the variety of soil properties in the maps that are produced. Furthermore, the process of collecting, analysing, interpreting, and creating maps from soil samples is tedious, expensive, and time-consuming. Thus, the combination of GIS, GPS, and VRT technologies gives farmers a previously unheard-of capacity to examine field maps and apply input where and when it is required to guarantee crop output (Sishodia, 2020).

2. **Soil quality assessment:** Assessments of soil quality help in managing soil, using its functions optimally, and preventing soil degradation by nourished future use. It also identifies soil patterns and their relationships that can help optimise soil fertility. Satellite remote sensing data and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are used to assess soil quality by storing, retrieving, and manipulating data to calculate and map soil parameters (Rahman *et al.*, 2017). It also identifies soil patterns and their relationships that can help optimise soil fertility.
3. **Soil nutrient distribution assessment:** Through the use of GIS to analyse the nutrient status of the field and identify nutrient deficiencies, agricultural producers may more accurately distribute nutrients from the outside (Ghosh, 2022). Based on the nutrient status, fertiliser recommendations can be given that might greatly increase crop yields, lower the cost of over-fertiliser, and give the crops balanced nutrition. (Kumar *et al.*, 2021).
4. **Crop monitoring:** Monitoring crop health and growth, as well as making an accurate or nearly correct yield projection, are essential for analysing food production and calculating economic return, which aids in managing food security. Numerous studies have demonstrated the potential for poor assessment and inaccurate area of crops appraisal resulting from the use of traditional methodologies for agricultural yield calculation. Furthermore, these approaches necessitate the collecting of costly, time-consuming, and labour-intensive crop and yield data (Soomro, 2015). This is where tools like GPS, GIS, and remote sensing (RS) come in extremely helpful because they can be used to measure the spatial and temporal variability of crop dynamics and yield output. It tracks crop health, their growth pattern, and yield forecasts through drone and satellite imagery. It identifies areas that need attention, such as nutrient deficiencies and disease outbreaks, and thus maximises their land's potential and increases crop yields. Using historical and current agricultural data from satellites, EOS Data Analytics (EOSDA), a company that provides satellite-powered data analytics and imagery analysis for agriculture and forestry, has created a dependable method for predicting crop production with an accuracy of above 90% (Hanh *et al.*, 2017).
5. **Pest and disease control:** Geographic Information Systems (GIS) offer useful tools for tracking, forecasting, controlling, and halting the spread of pests and agricultural diseases. The instruments provide chances for effective and economical control and intervention targeting. GIS can be used in monitoring to link an illness to auxiliary spatial data, discover spatial patterns of the disease, and assess the disease's spatial extent (Bouwmeester *et al.*, 2010). Additionally, GIS may be used to quantify shifting pest and disease thresholds brought on by climate change, forecast the anticipated spatial spread of illnesses, and supply data for risk assessment models in pest management. A system for detecting pests and diseases employs sophisticated picture recognition algorithms to spot possible dangers before they become major issues. It makes it possible to minimise crop losses, apply targeted treatments, use less pesticides, and protect beneficial insects.
6. **Water or Irrigation management:** GIS not only shows the amount of rainfall or soil moisture in each region, but it also shows where water drains more or less fast, allowing engineers to take appropriate action to balance the situation. Water stress is often identified using Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) or Normalised Difference Moisture Index (NDMI) indicators. Before the issue gets out of control, NDMI can identify water stress early on. Additionally, NDMI monitoring of irrigation greatly enhances crop growth, particularly in regions where crops need more water than nature can provide (Keria *et al.*, 2024). The NDMI index, which runs from -1 to 1 and is by default included in EOSDA Crop Monitoring, offers a concise description of the information acquired. Positive values around 1 may suggest waterlogging, whilst negative ones near -1 indicate water shortages (Hanh *et al.*, 2017).
7. **Assessing damage during hazard:** GIS is a useful tool for planning mitigation methods and determining the

amount and severity of damage caused by tornadoes, high winds, floods, fires, and many other comparable occurrences. Spatial analysis in GIS can be used in the evaluation of the spatial autocorrelation of natural hazards, and in combination with the areas prone to multiple environmental hazards, it can predict the risk and severity of damages in the future (Ghorbani *et al.*, 2023).

8. **Land Use Planning:** In order to maximise land efficiency, it is essential to comprehend the current land cover and use in an area. It makes it possible to make well-informed decisions about resource management, agriculture, urban planning, and conservation. Having accurate information enables stakeholders to maximise land use for sustainable growth. GIS can help planners analyse land use trends and distribution and determine future developments. It can also help planners to explore different land use scenarios and select the most suitable plan for agriculture and other activities (Elmabod *et al.*, 2019).
9. **Supply chain management:** Managing suppliers, producers, and consumers as a single unit is the goal of supply chain management, which aims to keep the entire chain competitive at the lowest possible cost. It also optimises routes and storage facilities for effective food distribution and reduced wastage. GIS can help manage agricultural supply chains by integrating data on farm locations, transportation routes, and market demand. This can help optimise logistics and distribution and reduce spoilage. (Ghosh, 2022)
10. **Hunger awareness:** Geographic Information Systems are contributing to the effort to increase awareness of the issue of world hunger, which is closely linked to agricultural resources, in order to meet the huge demand for food that exists today and will exist in the future. Information revealed from geoinformatics data plays a major role in predicting climatic conditions, making agricultural decisions, and formulating policies related to food security and cultivation activities (Chakrawarti *et al.*, 2024).
11. **Livestock monitoring:** In animal husbandry, tracking the movements of animals requires the use of agricultural GIS software. Using GIS agricultural tools, farmers may locate livestock on a farm and monitor their growth, nutrition, fertility, and overall health. GIS can help farmers locate livestock on a farm and monitor their movements, health, growth, fertility, and nutrition of livestock; map disease patterns and facilitate early intervention; help identify veterinary resources and enable targeted interventions during outbreaks; optimise grazing and improve overall productivity; analyse epidemiological information; reduce soil erosion by increasing environmental sustainability; and assess animal behaviour characteristics and pasture utilisation (Tadesse *et al.*, 2021).

Conclusion:

GIS has rapidly increased in use in agriculture over the last few decades as a crucial supplementary technology for assessing crops, soils, and their ecosystems. GIS is utilised throughout the entire crop life cycle, from planting to harvesting, as this article explains. The capabilities and insights offered by GIS, such as the most recent developments in real-time data collection and analysis, have further increased its significance in providing location/spatial intelligence required to increase farm productivity and profitability through precision farming methods and, consequently, food security. GIS is essential to attaining sustainable agricultural productivity and plays a part in food production thanks to its present and developing uses in conjunction with both newer and established partner technologies.

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